

D13.1 First release of the EOSC Execution Framework

Software Release Report

31/08/2025

Abstract

This is the release report for the first version of the EOSC Execution Framework. It contains information about its components, capabilities and associated software repositories. A detailed description of the architecture and capabilities will be available in D13.2 First report on EOSC Execution Framework Architecture and capabilities, to be delivered at M18 (September 2025).

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Executive summary

This document reports on the initial software release of the EOSC Execution Framework (EF), designed to streamline service integration and application deployment within the EOSC.

The two main components of the EOSC EF, the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) Registry and the EOSC Deployment Service, have been extended and integrated with the EOSC User Space. The key highlights and achievements of the first release include:

- Extension of the EOSC IF Registry with Configuration Templates for interoperability guidelines. This moves beyond human-readable guidelines to a more structured, machine-readable approach, with templates defined for areas like research product onboarding and monitoring integration.
- Creation of a new guideline for TOSCA Deployable Services.
- Extension of the EOSC Deployment Service to automate the registration of fully qualified and secure domain names for deployed services via a dynamic DNS service and the automated data staging capabilities to fetch datasets from multiple open repositories and make them available to dynamically provisioned virtual infrastructure.
- Extension of the User Space with the notion of Deployable Services: Deployable Services are discoverable via the Discovery Hub, users can request them and view their deployed services in a dedicated section.

An initial version of the composability-based applications to showcase and demonstrate the new capabilities have also been released:

- Scholarly Communication Metadata Aggregator for EOSC Nodes: Allows users to search for OAI-PMH compatible EOSC data sources, request metadata harvesting, and receive download links via email upon completion.
- Data Transfer Application: Successfully integrated with the EOSC User Space, enabling users to search for a dataset on the Discovery Hub, select it and staging it in a cloud infrastructure
- Setting up Data Analysis Environments: Demonstrated for the NFDI EOSC Pilot Node, this application combines customized virtualized infrastructure deployment with dynamic data fetching

The requirements and use cases defined in D10.2 are foreseen to be fully implemented under WP14, in accordance with the project planning for the second phase of the EOSC Beyond project.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and purpose of the document

This document reports on the initial release of the EOSC Execution Framework (EF), comprising the EOSC Interoperability Framework Registry and the EOSC Deployment Service, as well as the composable applications that leverage the EF.

We also include information about the software changes of the Front Office and the Discovery Hub that have been released to integrate with the EOSC EF.

A detailed description of the architecture and capabilities will be available in D13.2 'First report on EOSC Execution Framework Architecture and Capabilities', to be delivered at M18 (September 2025).

1.2. Structure of the document

The deliverable is organised as follows:

- **Section 2** describes the main components of the EOSC Execution Framework, outlines their capabilities, and lists the related software repositories.
- **Section 3** provides the conclusions.
- **Section 4** lists references.

2. Components, Capabilities and Software Repositories

This section summarises the components and capabilities of the EOSC Execution Framework that have been added and/or updated during the period M1 to M18 of the EOSC Beyond project. It also provides details of the software repositories that underpin them.

2.1. Components

The EOSC Execution Framework (EF) consists of two components:

- The EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) registry is a database designed to contain Interoperability Guideline profiles. This registry enables providers to align their services and products with specific guidelines, thereby indicating compatibility and composability features with other EOSC resources or core components. By recording these guidelines, the registry enhances the overall interoperability within the EOSC ecosystem. During M1-M18, the IF registry has been enriched with configuration templates associated to interoperability guidelines;
- The EOSC Deployment Service (DS), implemented through the Infrastructure Manager (IM), is an open-source service to deploy complex applications on multiple Cloud back-ends (AWS, OpenStack, etc.). It performs virtualised infrastructure provision, automatic software deployment and lifecycle management of these applications. It supports the OASIS TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) standard for application architecture description. During M1-M18, a new guideline for TOSCA Deployable Services has been created and registered in the IF registry, the DS has been extended to support the automated registration of DNS hostnames and to support automated data staging capabilities.

The EF is integrated with the EOSC User Space.

The implementation of the composability-based applications leveraging the EF has also started:

- Scholarly Communication Metadata Aggregator for EOSC Nodes;
- Data Transfer;
- Setting up a data analysis environment.

2.2. Capabilities

2.2.1. IF Registry Enhancements

The EOSC IF Registry is evolving from a collection of human-readable guidelines to a collection of guidelines that support [machine-composability of resources](#).

The new capabilities offered to providers are:

- Definition of Configuration Templates for an Interoperability Guideline. Configuration Templates are structured profiles through which services can expose information about the actual API endpoints as described by the EOSC guidelines they are compliant with. Guideline Providers can define one or more Configuration Templates for a specific Guideline based on a specific definition schema. Currently, definition through the GUI is done using a simple text editor but this will change to a more structured and user-friendly editor in the second half of the project. Configuration template definitions can also be created and managed via the REST API of the EOSC IF Registry. Configuration Templates have been created for the IF guidelines for:
 - Data Sources to onboard Research Products
 - Monitoring integration.
- Definition of Configuration Instances for onboarded Services that adhere to Guidelines with Configuration Templates. Service Providers can instantiate configurations for their services based on the Guideline Configuration Template in the Providers Portal. Similarly, definition through the GUI is done using a simple text editor for now. The same can be done using a REST API on the Service Registry.
- Configuration Instances are now persisted in the Service Registry and are part of the data that the Service Catalogue shares with other Core Components (particularly the User Space) through messaging or API.

2.2.2. EOSC Deployment Service Enhancements

The EOSC Deployment Service (DS), based on the Infrastructure Manager, enables the support of automated provisioning and configuration of deployable services and virtualised computing infrastructure through standard TOSCA templates and DevOps tools (e.g. Ansible) for automated configuration of computational resources.

Existing capabilities of the EOSC Deployment Service allows fetching of TOSCA templates from TOSCA template repositories and the automated deployment of services in EOSC Cloud Resources.

During M1-M18, the EOSC Deployment Service has been extended to:

- Create and register in the IF Registry a new guideline for TOSCA Deployable Services.
- Register and assign fully qualified and secure domain names to deployed services via a dynamic DNS service. The DNS service API has been extended to support the automated registration of DNS hostnames, and the DS has been updated to use the new API in the deployment process.

- Support automated data staging capabilities to fetch data from multiple open repositories and make it available to the dynamically provisioned virtual infrastructure. For that, a set of custom types has been defined to describe the concept of a DataSet node and the DS has been extended to support the fetching of the datasets into the deployed set of virtual machines.

2.2.3. Enhancements to the EOSC User Space

According to the technical roadmap defined in D10.2 [1], the User Space has also been extended and integrated with the EOSC EF. In this section, we highlight the enhancements implemented during M1-M18 to achieve the integration between the EF and the User Space, in particular with the EOSC Discovery Hub, Front Office, and Providers' Hub to improve service deployability and accessibility within the EOSC ecosystem. To accomplish this, we first prepared the designs and then implemented them.

Designs Overview

- **Front Office**
 - Design of a detailed page for Deployable Services.
 - Implementation of a custom, three-step *Offer Ordering Form*:
 1. Configure technical parameters defined in a TOSCA template,
 2. Optionally provide the DOI of a dataset to be transferred to the cloud,
 3. Select the preferred cloud infrastructure for deployment.
- **Discovery Hub**
 - Introduction of a dedicated list view for Deployable Services, featuring advanced filtering and a card-based presentation layout,
 - Include Deployable Services in the projects view,
 - Design of a detailed view for individual deployments of Deployable Services, presenting e.g. their deployment status and environment address.

Development Highlights

- **Front Office**
 - Implemented function to retrieve Deployable Services from the Service Catalogue and expose them via a public API.
 - Implemented function to manually generate an offer based on the TOSCA template specified in a URL parameter.
 - Implemented a detailed view for the Deployable Service page.
 - Developed and integrated the three-step *Offer Ordering Form*.
- **Discovery Hub**
 - Implemented a dedicated list view for Deployable Services, with advanced search and filtering functionality.
 - Developed the User Space for viewing Deployable Services deployments.
 - Implemented detailed views for individual deployments of Deployable Services.

- **Integration**

- Ensured seamless integration between the EOSC User Space and the EOSC Deployment Service.

2.2.4. Composability-based application: Scholarly Communication Metadata Aggregator for EOSC Nodes

The first release allows users to search for EOSC data sources that are compatible with the OAI-PMH protocol, select one and request the harvesting of its metadata records (see [Figure 1](#)). The user is then notified about the completion of the process via email, with a message that includes a link from which the user can download the collected metadata records (see [Figure 2](#)).

Figure 1. EOSC Metadata Harvester GUI

Success Notification: Metadata Collection Request (ID: coll-e7c630f0-3a93-4409-8bdd-52b345f8ec6a)

OAI Collector Service [REDACTED] 13
[REDACTED]

Dear [REDACTED]

I hope this email finds you well. I am writing to inform you that your request to collect metadata from the provided URL has been completed successfully.
Request ID: coll-e7c630f0-3a93-4409-8bdd-52b345f8ec6a
URL: <https://datacatalogue.cesda.eu/oai-qmh/v0/oai>
Collected Records: 1000

You can now download your file by visiting the following address:
<https://ip-90-147-152-76.na2.garmentservices.io/oai-collector-service/download/coll-e7c630f0-3a93-4409-8bdd-52b345f8ec6a>

Should you require more detailed information, please feel free to invoke the following API:
<https://ip-90-147-152-76.na2.garmentservices.io/oai-collector-service/api/history/coll-e7c630f0-3a93-4409-8bdd-52b345f8ec6a>

If you have any further questions or need assistance, please don't hesitate to reach out. We are here to help!

Best Regards,

EOSC Metadata Harvester daemon

Note: This is an automatically generated message. Please do not reply directly to this email.

Figure 2. Email from the EOSC Metadata Harvester upon successful harvesting

2.2.5. Composability-based application: Data Transfer

The Data Transfer application addresses a common scenario of staging datasets in a cloud infrastructure where they will be later processed, analysed, or used for the training of AI models. These datasets may be large in size or contain many files, and having a data transfers management workflow is convenient and key for scalability and reliability.

This exemplary application deploys a new infrastructure in EGI's federation with a custom dataset in it. When requesting (or *ordering*) this application (or *deployment*), the user inputs one or more DOIs associated with data sources (e.g., Zenodo records). The amount of data in the given DOI record(s) is evaluated, and the Deployment Service is then requested to create the new infrastructure – a new virtual machine with enough storage capacity, computing and network resources necessary – with the corresponding datasets.

Once the new infrastructure is set and the copying of datasets from the specified DOI is finished, the user is handed the necessary information to connect to it – IP address and login credentials, for instance.

The Data Transfer API has been integrated also in the landing pages of datasets with DOIs in the Discovery Hub. In particular, users can select a dataset with a DOI and the dataset landing page (implemented by EOSC EXPLORE) has an option to use the service (see [Figure 3](#)). The GUI allows users to select (i) the specific version of the dataset they are interested in; (ii) the dataset files to transfer (all or a subset); (iii) the type of destination and other parameters required to complete the transfer.

Figure 3. EOSC Data Transfer: integration in EOSC EXPLORE

2.2.6. Composability-based application: Setting up data analysis environment

This section includes an example of a composability-based application that combines the deployment of customized virtualized infrastructure with the dynamic fetching of data from open repositories to create a data analysis environment. The general procedure is described in *D13.2 First report on EOSC Execution Framework Architecture and capabilities*, section 2.4.1 *Setting up a Data Analysis Environment*. This section describes a particular application of that procedure for the NFDI EOSC Pilot Node (from now on, NFDI), which leverages the composability capabilities provided by the EOSC Deployment Service.

Figure 4. A sample composability-based application for the NFDI EOSC Pilot Node

Figure 4 describes the approach employed. NFDI provides, among other services, the **DESY Public Data Repository**, which includes a dataset as part of an initial test of DESY Public Data integration with DataCite for DOI minting. **This dataset** is a compiled dataset of raw X-ray reflectivity (XRR, reflectometry) measurements together with corresponding fit

parameters, intentionally published to use as training or test data for machine learning models.

The extensions introduced in the TOSCA specification to support the definition of datasets stored in data repositories have been made available in the EOSC Deployment Service deployed in the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. This way, users can choose a specific TOSCA Template, which defines the application architecture and software required for the dataset analysis (in this case a Virtual Machine (VM) with at least 4 GB of RAM and Jupyter installed) and indicate the location of the dataset via its DOI. The EOSC Deployment Service then:

1. Provisions the required VM from the underlying IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) Cloud the user has access to. In this particular case, the EGI Cloud Compute service was employed.
2. Configures the VM with the precise software configuration via the Ansible Roles that are indicated in the TOSCA template. In this case, additional block storage was required to host the dataset and Jupyter support was installed.
3. Automatically retrieves the dataset from the data repository and makes it available for the data processing engine selected. For that, the [DataHugger library](#) was integrated to facilitate the resolution of DOIs and provide access to data.

This composability-based application coordinates the usage of different services (EGI Check-In, EOSC Deployment Service, EGI Cloud Compute) for the users to mix-and-match data analysis applications with datasets to facilitate the dynamic deployment of data analysis environments that scientists can access remotely. Further technical details about the corresponding TOSCA template are provided in section [2.3.5. Additional information](#) regarding takeaways from the NFDI Pilot Node preparation in EOSC Beyond is available [here](#).

2.3. Software repositories

2.3.1. IF Registry

Attribute	Details
Name	EOSC Interoperability Framework Registry
Location (URL)	https://github.com/madgeek-arc/resource-catalogue
Licence	Apache 2.0
Release number	5.0.0
Documentation (URLs)	ReadMe: https://github.com/cyfronet-fid/marketplace-core/blob/master/README.md Deployment Guide:

Attribute	Details
	<p>https://providers.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/docs/EOSC_Service_Catalogue_update_2025/EOSC_Deployment_IFDB_up_25/</p> <p>HowTo: https://providers.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/docs/</p> <p>API: https://providers.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/docs/EOSC_Service_Catalogue_update_2025/EOSC_Index_Interoperability_up_25/</p> <p>Release Notes: https://github.com/madgeek-arc/resource-catalogue/releases</p>
SQAaaS rating	Bronze
TRL	8 (The software is stable, reliable and has been deployed in the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. A Terms of Use policy is in place, as is a Core Participation Agreement.)

Table 1: IF Registry software repository details

2.3.2. EOSC Deployment Service

Attribute	Details
Name	EOSC Deployment Service
Location (URL)	https://github.com/grycap/im
Licence	GPL-3.0
Release number	1.19.0
Documentation (URLs)	<p>ReadMe: https://github.com/grycap/im/blob/master/README.md</p> <p>User Guide: https://imdocs.readthedocs.io/</p> <p>Release Notes: https://github.com/grycap/im/releases</p>
SQAaaS rating	Gold
TRL	8 (The software is stable, reliable - as shown by the availability monitoring statistics - and has been deployed in the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. There are users who are making real use of it and rely on it for their work. A Terms of Use policy is in place, as is a Core Participation Agreement.)

Table 2: EOSC Deployment Service software repository details

Attribute	Details
Name	Front Office
Location (URL)	https://github.com/cyfronet-fid/marketplace
Licence	GPL-3.0
Release number	3.59.1
Documentation (URLs)	<p>ReadMe: https://github.com/cyfronet-fid/marketplace/blob/master/README.md</p> <p>Change Log: https://github.com/cyfronet-fid/marketplace/blob/development/CHANGELOG.md</p> <p>Release Notes: https://github.com/cyfronet-fid/marketplace/releases</p> <p>Search API: https://marketplace.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/api_docs/swagger/index.html?urls.primaryName=EOSC%20Marketplace%20search%20API</p> <p>Offering API: https://marketplace.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/api_docs/swagger/index.html?urls.primaryName=EOSC%20Marketplace%20Offering%20API</p> <p>Ordering API: https://marketplace.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/api_docs/swagger/index.html?urls.primaryName=EOSC%20Marketplace%20Ordering%20API</p>
SQAaaS rating	Silver
TRL	8 (The software is stable, reliable (as shown by the availability monitoring statistics) and has been deployed in the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. There are users who are making real use of it and rely on it for their work. A Terms of Use policy is in place, as is a Core Participation Agreement.)

Table 3: EOSC Front Office software repository details

Attribute	Details
Name	Discovery Hub
Location (URL)	https://github.com/cyfronet-fid/eosc-search-service/

Attribute	Details
Licence	GPL-3.0
Release number	2.30.0
Documentation (URLs)	<p>ReadMe: https://github.com/cyfronet-fid/eosc-search-service/blob/development/README.md</p> <p>Change Log: https://github.com/cyfronet-fid/eosc-search-service/blob/development/CHANGELOG.md</p> <p>Release Notes: https://github.com/cyfronet-fid/eosc-search-service/releases</p>
SQAaaS rating	Not yet rated
TRL	8 (The software is stable, reliable (as shown by the availability monitoring statistics) and has been deployed in the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. There are users who are making real use of it and rely on it for their work. A Terms of Use policy is in place, as is a Core Participation Agreement.)

Table 4: EOSC Discovery Hub software repository details

2.3.3. Composability-based application: Scholarly Communication Metadata Aggregator for EOSC Nodes

Attribute	Details
Name	Simple OAI Collector Service
Location (URL)	https://code-repo.d4science.org/michele.artini/simpleOaiCollectorService
Licence	AGPL-3.0
Release number	1.0.0
Documentation (URLs)	<p>ReadMe: https://code-repo.d4science.org/michele.artini/simpleOaiCollectorService</p> <p>API: https://ip-90-147-152-76.na2.garrservices.it/oai-collector-service</p> <p>Release Notes: https://code-repo.d4science.org/michele.artini/simpleOaiCollectorService/releases/tag/simple-oai-collector-1.0.0</p>

Attribute	Details
SQAaaS rating	Not yet rated
TRL	6 (Technology demonstrated in relevant environment)

Table 5: OAI Collector Service software repository details

Attribute	Details
Name	EOSC Metadata Harvester GUI
Location (URL)	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/eosc-metadata-harvester
Licence	Apache 2.0
Release number	1.0.0
Documentation (URLs)	ReadMe: https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/eosc-metadata-harvester/src/tag/1.0.0/README.md Release Notes: https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/eosc-metadata-harvester/releases
SQAaaS rating	Not yet rated
TRL	6 (Technology demonstrated in relevant environment)

Table 6: EOSC Metadata Harvester GUI software repository details

2.3.4. Composability-based application: Data Transfer

Attribute	Details
Name	EOSC EXPLORE integration with Data Transfer
Location (URL)	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/eosc-explore
Licence	Apache 2.0
Release number	5.0.0
Documentation (URLs)	ReadMe: https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/eosc-explore/src/tag/5.0.0/README.md Release Notes: https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/eosc-explore/releases
SQAaaS rating	Not yet rated

Attribute	Details
TRL	8 (The software is stable, reliable (as shown by the availability monitoring statistics) and has been deployed in the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. There are users who are making real use of it and rely on it for their work. A Terms of Use policy is in place, as is a Core Participation Agreement.)

Table 7: EOSC EXPLORE integration with Data Transfer software repository details

2.3.5. Composability-based application: Setting up data analysis environment

Attribute	Details
Name	TOSCA Template for the Deploy of a Data Analysis Environment
Location (URL)	https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/eosc_beyond/templates/jupyter_doi.yml
Licence	Apache 2.0
Release number	N/A
Documentation (URLs)	https://github.com/grycap/tosca/blob/eosc_beyond/templates/jupyter_doi.yml (Description embedded in the metadata fields and in the inputs section of the TOSCA template)
SQAaaS rating	N/A - A TOSCA template is not a standalone software repository but rather deploys a complete virtualized infrastructure composed of multiple software applications and services.
TRL	N/A

Table 8: Setting up data analysis environment software repository details

3. Conclusion

The first release of the EOSC Execution Framework (EF) represents a significant milestone, successfully delivering its components and demonstrating their enhanced capabilities via three composability-based applications.

Key highlights and achievements

- IF Registry and the Providers' Portal of the EOSC User Space have been enhanced to support the definition of Configuration Templates for interoperability guidelines and the creation of configuration instances for onboarded services. Specific Configuration Templates have been defined for the interoperability guidelines for onboarding research products and for monitoring integration.
- A new IF Guideline for TOSCA Deployable Services has been defined and added to the IF Registry.
- The EOSC Deployment Service has been extended to:
 - Automate the registration of fully qualified and secure domain names
 - Provide automated data staging capabilities, allowing the fetching of datasets from open repositories to a dynamically provisioned virtual infrastructure
- Seamless integration with the Discovery Hub of the User Space: significant design and development efforts ensured the integration of the EOSC Deployment Service with the EOSC User Space. This includes new list views, detailed pages for Deployable Services, a user-friendly three-step Offer Ordering Form, and a dedicated section for the users to view their deployments.
- The preparation work on the composability-based applications demonstrates the use of the extended Execution Framework, setting the stage for their final implementation during WP14
 - Scholarly Communication Metadata Aggregator for EOSC Nodes: this application enables users to search and harvest metadata records from OAI-PMH compatible EOSC data sources, with email notifications and download links for collected metadata
 - Data Transfer Application has been successfully integrated with the EOSC Deployment Service and EOSC EXPLORE, for convenient dataset selection and transfer.
 - Setting up Data Analysis Environments: This application combines customized virtual infrastructure deployment with dynamic data fetching, as demonstrated for the NFDI EOSC Pilot Node. It utilizes TOSCA templates to provision virtual machines, configure software (e.g., Jupyter), and automatically retrieve datasets via DOIs, coordinating various services to create remote data analysis environments

The fundamental components of the extended EOSC Execution Framework have reached TRL8, indicating their stability and reliability.

Outlook and next steps

The first release of the EOSC Execution Framework (EF) establishes a robust foundation, and the focus will now shift towards finalizing the implementation and expanding the capabilities required to fully support the use case scenarios and epics outlined in the technical roadmap ([D10.2](#)).

Future developments in WP14, in line with the activities foreseen for the second phase of the EOSC Beyond project, include:

- A more structured and user-friendly editor for the definition of Configuration Templates in the Providers' Portal of the EOSC User Space.
- EOSC Deployment Service extended to automatically request TLS certificates.
- Registration of the composability-based applications in the EOSC Service Catalogue
- Integration of Data Transfer in the Scholarly Communication Metadata Aggregator for EOSC Node application and in the EOSC Deployment Service

4. References

1. Brandt, C. H., Papastefanatos, G., Kołomański, M., Moltó, G., Manghi, P., & Thermolia, C. (2025). EOSC Beyond D10.2 Report on EOSC Integration Suite and Execution Framework Requirements and Gap Analysis v.2 (V1.0 UNDER EC REVIEW). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15100920>
2. Martinez, A. B., Fuhrmann, P., Wetzel, T. (2025). Takeaways from the NFDI pilot node preparation in EOSC Beyond. EGI 2025 Book of Abstracts. <https://indico.eji.eu/event/6638/book-of-abstracts.pdf> (Last accessed 20 August 2025). Presentation slides: https://indico.eji.eu/event/6638/contributions/20478/attachments/16581/22017/20250604_EOSC-Nodes_Wetzel.pdf (Last accessed 20 August 2025).

Acronym	Meaning
DS	Deployment Service
DTS	Data Transfer Service
EF	Execution Framework
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IF	Interoperability Framework
IG	Interoperability Guideline
IS	Integration Suite
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur
SQAaaS	Software Quality Assurance as a Service
VM	Virtual Machine

Table 9: Acronyms